

Bimanual grape manipulation for human-inspired robotic harvesting

Sotiris Stavridis*, Leonidas Droukas and Zoe Doulgeri

Abstract—Most existing robotic harvesters utilize a unimanual approach with a single arm grasping and detaching the crop, either via a detachment movement, or stem cutting by a specially designed gripper/cutter end-effector. However, such unimanual solutions cannot be applied for sensitive crops and cluttered environments like grapes, where obstacles may occlude the stem, leaving no space for the cutter’s placement. In such cases, the solution would require a bimanual robot that visually unveils the stem, while manipulating the grasped crop to create cutting affordances. Considering grapes vertical trellis setups, a dual-arm coordinated motion control methodology is proposed in this work for reaching a stem pre-cut state. The camera equipped arm with the cutter reaches the stem, visually unveiling it, while the second arm moves the grasped grape towards the surrounding free-space, facilitating its stem cutting. In-lab experimental validation and extensive evaluation in a real vineyard with the BACCHUS¹ bimanual harvesting platform demonstrate the performance of the proposed approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, development of robotic technologies and their application in agricultural tasks are becoming a growing topic of interest [1]. The rising of food supply demands, climate change, land degradation and arable land limitations have all pushed towards agricultural productivity growth becoming an important priority. Incorporating advanced, automated, agricultural technologies is bound to greatly benefit productivity and in turn economic development [2], while at the same time facilitating and improving the difficult working conditions of farmers and agricultural workers [3]. In this context, an increasing amount of research work has been noticed during the last years, regarding a variety of agricultural robotic applications such as crop monitoring, phenotyping, yield estimation, maturity assessment, disease identification, pruning, weeding as well as harvesting [4]–[8]. Selective crop harvesting has been lately adopted, with the robot first detecting the target crop and then harvesting it, as it entails less danger of harming the crops and the trees compared to bulk harvesting [9]. The selective approach enables harvesting of crops that meet certain criteria, most commonly linked to desired maturity levels.

The majority of the proposed integrated robotic solutions for harvesting are unimanual [6]. They utilize one robotic manipulator responsible for monitoring the target crop via a mounted in-hand camera and harvesting it by grasping and

detaching it. In [10], [11] a detaching movement is performed by the arm’s gripper via pulling and twisting the grasped crop in order to cause the stem’s breaking and crop’s release. However, detaching movements are only applicable on rigid crops (e.g. apples) that can withstand such treatment without being damaged. Other unimanual approaches in the cases eggplants, cucumbers, tomatoes and strawberries, harvest the crop by cutting its stem involving specialized cutting tools embodied in the gripper [12], [13] or specialized cutter end-effectors, that can simultaneously cut and hold the crop by its stem [14], [15]. Such robotic harvesting solutions may work when cultivation/farming methods are specifically designed to facilitate them, like the cucumber high-wire system in [13] or after certain pre-harvesting activities like pruning as in the apple case [11]. Such solutions are not suitable for cluttered environments and sensitive crops, as is the case of wine grape vineyards, where poles, wires, branches, leaves and even the crops itself partially occlude the target stem, which can be further partially wrapped around a branch, leaving little to no space for the cutter’s placement. Humans who harvest grapes in these vineyards grasp the crop with one arm, moving their head and body to be able to see the stem, manipulate the crop, if needed, to provide sufficient free room around its stem to place the cutting tool held by their other arm (Fig. 1). In this work, we adopt a bimanual approach to grape harvesting similar to the human practice.

Bimanual robots have gained popularity as they can mimic human behaviors, act and manipulate objects in ways similar to humans and thus they can work interchangeably and in collaboration with humans in the same task. Generally, bimanual manipulation approaches and dual-arm manipulators have been utilized in many robotic applications summarized in the following survey papers [16]–[18]. Although, multi-manual robots increase the complexity of the overall system, they offer multiple end-effectors to interact with the environment, thus allowing the execution of a broader range of complex tasks.

For harvesting, although multi-arm robots have been considered in various published works [19]–[21], the approach

Fig. 1: Bimanual human harvesting of grapes.

Authors are with the Automation & Robotics Lab, School of Electrical & Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece. Emails: {sotistav@ece.auth.gr, ldroukas@ece.auth.gr, doulgeri@ece.auth.gr} *Corresponding Author

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871704> & <https://bacchus-project.eu/>

is unimanual with each arm harvesting one crop/fruit at a time. There are only few works in literature, proposing a dual-arm/bimanual harvesting solution targeting tomatoes and aubergines [22]–[24]. In [22], [23], a dual-arm robot is designed, with two 3 degrees of freedom (dof) SCARA manipulators one equipped with a vacuum suction gripper and the other with a saw cutting tool and is evaluated in a simple environment with several potted tomatoes placed in rows. However, the few dof of the robot arms and the specific gripper design, limits this solution’s applicability to rigid, spherical crops. In [24], a dual-arm aubergine harvesting robot is proposed with the two arms harvesting crops in parallel except in the case of an occluded crop, in which they collaborate to physically unveil and harvest the occluded crop. However, this solution has only been validated in lab experiments and its performance in a real field deployment remains to be seen.

The following works were only found to address or are related to the case of grape harvesting, a delicate crop type [21], [25], [26]. The work in [21] proposes a parallel two arm solution for the case of harvesting grapes in horizontal trellis (pergola). In horizontal trellis the environment around the grapes is less cluttered because the grapes are hanging from above. In contrast, vertical trellis setups that are used in wine grape vineyards present a much more challenging harvesting environment. The work in [21] assumes the position of the grape stem based on the visible portion of the grape. It demonstrates promising results, i.e. a success rate of 85% and a harvesting time of 8.5 sec per grape, though in a rather limited number of trials (15). Again occlusions are not considered and explicit stem detection is not made, hence, the solution’s generalizability particularly in the case of vertical trellis is doubtful. The work in [25] and our previous work [26] are related to the grape harvesting in the sense that they deal with visual stem unveiling. The work in [25] proposes an exploration-based view planning method that optimizes a scene coverage metric with a path length cost function to unveil an occluded grape stem in a few steps, with a reported stem detection rate of 68.7% and average stem detection time 66.4 sec in the real field. In our previous work [26], we follow a control-based approach for unveiling the stem and validate it with in lab experiments.

This work addresses for the first time the problem of autonomous grape harvesting in the challenging environment of vertical trellis setups contrary to [21]. It is inspired by the way humans harvest grapes (Fig.1) and hence utilizes a bimanual robot with two 6 dof robotic arms. One arm is equipped with a gripper (from now on, referred to as “grasping arm”) and the other with a stem cutting tool and a camera mounted upon its end-effector (referred to as “camera arm”). It proposes a novel bimanual kinematic controller in order to properly view the stem and create the necessary cutting affordances to enable the cutter’s placement. The proposed method resolves the core bimanual harvesting task in an efficient and effective manner and is extensively evaluated in a real vineyard as part of the whole harvesting procedure in contrast to [25] and [26] which only deal with the stem unveiling part. Based on the point cloud of the scene and its

processing, estimates of the required by the control critical point positions are made and used to generate a reference velocity signal for the kinematically controlled bimanual robot. For the grasping arm, we propose the use of the most distant point from any obstacle in the spherical projection of the scene in order to calculate the position control target for the pulling of the grape to generate space for the cutter’s placement. The considered task of grape harvesting involves a number of technical challenges that, to the best of our knowledge, are not addressed in other dual-arm robotic tasks. These challenges include: (a) the manipulation of a flexible hinged object with unknown lengths via stretching, in contrast to existing applications (e.g. rotating a door to open/close it) where rigid objects of constant, known radial length are considered; (b) the visual unveiling of a dynamic target, such as the manipulated stem, within a heavily cluttered, dynamic environment, such as leaves and branches being moved by air drafts, whereas existing works usually consider a modelled environment and a rigid target, both known and static; (c) the bimanual orchestration and the robotic arms motion synchronization via timing and conditional dependency of the tasks, in order to execute the grape harvesting successfully.

The rest of this work is structured as follows. Section II outlines the harvesting procedure and formulates the problem we address in this work. Section III details the proposed control methodology. Section IV report on the method’s validation with lab experiments. Section V presents field experimental results that demonstrate and evaluate the effectiveness and performance of the method in real conditions and Sections VI concludes and discusses the findings of this work and our future work plans.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

We follow a human inspired bimanual grape harvesting procedure which is outlined in Fig. 2 and requires both uncoordinated and coordinated bimanual arm motion. At first the target grape is detected by the side camera and using a cylindrical object model, grasping candidates are generated and the best grasp pose is selected. The grasping arm is equipped with a gripper with customized 3D printed fingers in order to enclose the grape variety that needs to be harvested. The camera arm monitors the whole scene via a mounted, in-hand, RGB-D camera and is also equipped with a cutting tool. The camera arm is reaching towards the grape (region of interest-ROI) in order to detect and maximize stem visibility and the grasping arm moves towards the grasping pose. These two tasks are independent but can be executed simultaneously, given the self collision avoidance method implemented in the system [27] (Fig. 2 - uncoordinated). Detailed presentation of vision algorithms for the detection of the target grape cluster and the stem are beyond the scope of this work. One may find a significant amount of related published works [28]–[30] from which [29] and [30] were used in this work. Once the stem is detected, and the grape is grasped, the manipulation of the grasped grape to maximize the cutting affordances of its stem can start. As the induced motion of the grape might affect the visibility of its stem which should be kept inside the in-hand camera’s field of view, grape manipulation is coordinated

Fig. 2: BACCHUS harvesting procedure flowchart. Green colored: grasping arm tasks. Red colored: camera arm tasks.

with stem visual unveiling (Fig. 2 - coordinated asymmetrical). Such coordination facilitates the camera arm for reaching to cut the stem as it remains in the vicinity. Stem cutting involves only the camera arm’s motion, while the grasping arm holds on its position until cutting is completed (Fig. 2 - coordinated asymmetrical). The final part that completes the harvesting process is the transfer of the detached grasped grape into the container which is a unimanual task (Fig. 2 - unimanual).

In this work, we focus on the coordinated bimanual task in Fig. 2 of manipulating the grasped grape to maximize the cutting affordances of its stem, while maximizing stem visibility by visual unveiling. Notice that the method implies stem detection hence a partially visible stem. In the case of a fully occluded stem, physical unveiling may also be applied given a bimanual robot. Physical unveiling has already been used for occluded aubergines [24]. We have also used in BACCHUS a harvesting pipeline branch not depicted in Fig. 2 for physically unveiling the stem when fully occluded [31].

The coordinated asymmetrical bimanual manipulation starts when the stem of the target grape is detected and the target grape is grasped. As soon as a stem is detected a point-cloud of the overall scene is provided by the camera to the system. Let $\mathbf{q}_g \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g}$ be the joint position vector of the grasping arm and $\mathbf{q}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{N_c}$ that of the camera arm. Let $\mathbf{T}_c \in SE(3)$ denote the pose of the camera’s frame $\{C\}$ (which is in our case placed at the camera arm’s tip) with respect to the world inertial frame $\{w\}$; it involves its position $\mathbf{p}_c(\mathbf{q}_c) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and its orientation $\mathbf{R}_c(\mathbf{q}_c) \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_c \ \mathbf{y}_c \ \mathbf{z}_c] \in SO(3)$, that are both known via the camera arm’s kinematics. Additionally, let $\mathbf{T}_g \in SE(3)$ denote the pose of the grasping arm’s frame $\{G\}$ with respect to $\{w\}$, involving position $\mathbf{p}_g(\mathbf{q}_g) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and orientation $\mathbf{R}_g(\mathbf{q}_g) \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_g \ \mathbf{y}_g \ \mathbf{z}_g] \in SO(3)$, known via the grasping arm’s kinematics.

A. Camera Arm Control Objectives

The camera arm’s task is that of ROI *reaching* and *centering* as well as stem *unveiling*. The ROI is defined by a sphere centered at the detected stem with $\mathbf{p}_r \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being its center in the inertia frame and $r \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ its radius set at a predefined value so that we get sufficiently close to the stem. The

respective algorithm is presented in detail in our previous work [26]. The aim is to reach a region of interest (ROI) surrounding the stem, while adopting a pose in this region that unveils the stem as much as possible.

For *reaching*, the control objective is formulated as follows: $\|\mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_c\| \rightarrow \bar{r} \leq r$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$ for some scalar positive \bar{r} , i.e. the camera arm’s end-effector should move in the ROI. For *centering*, the camera’s z-axis should be aligned with the vector pointing to the ROI center, securing the best ROI and stem viewpoint. The centering objective is formulated as follows: $\theta(\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_r) \rightarrow 0$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$ where $\theta(\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_r) \triangleq \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\mathbf{z}_c^T (\mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_c)}{\|\mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_c\|} \right)$ is the angle between $\mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_c$ and the camera’s view direction \mathbf{z}_c . Angle θ cannot be more than $\pi/2$, since \mathbf{p}_r is within the camera’s field of view.

Unveiling involves maximizing the stem’s visible part, i.e. the perceived number of the stem’s point-cloud points and is detailed in [26]. The unveiling and centering are crucial during the grape manipulation while the ROI reaching ensures that we stay in the spherical region centered in the stem.

Remark 1. *At the initial harvesting process state (Fig.2 - uncoordinated), there may not be enough information regarding the stem due to the distance from the targeted grape. In such cases the ROI center is placed on the target grape cluster, i.e. the median of the grape’s point cloud. When the stem is detected by the in-hand camera, the ROI center is updated and placed upon the median of the stem’s point cloud.*

B. Grasping Arm Control Objective

The grasping arm’s task is to manipulate the grasped grape to increase the stem cutting affordances while avoiding inducing possible occlusions by the grasping arm motion. The stem is stretched and moved towards a point, computed from the provided scene’s point-cloud, that is in the free space and most distant from the cutting tool to enable the cutter’s easier approach to the stem. Let this free-space point’s position be \mathbf{p}_{gd} , referred to as pull-point in the rest of the paper. We assume that $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, i.e. the actual applied force vector at the grasping arm’s tip, is measurable. Notice that the target grape cluster is an object hinged to a branch by its stem. We can estimate the

stem basis from the stem point-cloud and let $\mathbf{n}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the direction from the stem basis to \mathbf{p}_{gd} . We can then formulate the arm's control objective as a force position control objective along \mathbf{n}_c and its orthogonal subspace respectively. Let $f_d \in \mathbb{R}$ be an appropriately selected force magnitude for stretching the stem sufficiently without inflicting grape damage or slippage. The grasping arm's control objectives can be mathematically expressed as follows: For the force controller $\mathbf{n}_c \mathbf{n}_c^T \mathbf{f} \rightarrow \mathbf{n}_c f_d$ and for the position controller $(\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{n}_c \mathbf{n}_c^T)(\mathbf{p}_g - \mathbf{p}_{gd}) \rightarrow \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1}$. The purpose is to achieve accurately the reaching of the desired position coordinates on a plane normal to \mathbf{n}_c , thus reaching a point on the line passing through \mathbf{p}_{gd} . As this line is our force control space, the position coordinate along it, is determined indirectly by reaching the desired pulling force.

C. Bimanual Coordination Control Objective

The task of the camera arm is loosely coupled with that of the grasping arm since its motion during the grape manipulation may move the grape and the stem out of the camera's field of camera view. Hence, the camera arm should coordinate its motion with that of the grasping arm. Given the camera arm's objectives, this coordination task can be achieved by superimposing the grasping arm's translational velocity to that of the camera arm and compensating for the orientation to keep the stem centered in the camera view. Notice that we do not consider the grasping arm's rotational velocity in this coordination since any change in the grasping arm's orientation is not expected to significantly affect the stem position.

III. PROPOSED CONTROL METHODOLOGY

We consider a velocity controlled bimanual robot. Our control objective is to design a reference velocity control signal $\mathbf{V}_r = [\mathbf{V}_c^T \ \mathbf{V}_g^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$ involving the arm end-effector velocities $\mathbf{V}_c, \mathbf{V}_g \in \mathbb{R}^6$ for the cutting and grasping arm respectively. Velocity \mathbf{V}_r can be mapped to the joint space via the robot's extended Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) = \text{diag}(\mathbf{J}_c(\mathbf{q}_c), \mathbf{J}_g(\mathbf{q}_g)) \in \mathbb{R}^{12 \times (N_c + N_g)}$, involving the camera arm Jacobian $\mathbf{J}_c(\mathbf{q}_c) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times N_c}$ and the grasping arm Jacobian $\mathbf{J}_g(\mathbf{q}_g) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times N_g}$ as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger(\mathbf{q}) \mathbf{V}_r \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{q} = [\mathbf{q}_c^T \ \mathbf{q}_g^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N_c + N_g}$ denotes the robot's joint position and $\mathbf{J}^\dagger(\mathbf{q})$ is a pseudo inverse of the robot's extended Jacobian matrix.

Designing \mathbf{V}_c and \mathbf{V}_g is heavily based upon the overall scene's point-cloud set and its processing in order to estimate the required quantities involved in each control objective. The following subsections present the scene point-cloud process as well as the two arms control methodologies, proposed in this work; regarding the camera arm, its control scheme (\mathbf{V}_c) detailed in [26] is also briefly included here for completeness.

A. Scene Point-cloud Process and Calculations of Control Related Critical Point Positions

Let $\mathcal{W} : \{\mathbf{p}_{w_i} \in \mathbb{R}^3, i = 1, \dots, n_W\}$ be the set of $n_W \in \mathbb{N}$ points of the point-cloud captured by the camera with \mathbf{p}_{w_i}

being their position vector expressed in the world frame (Fig. 3a). Let subset $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{W} : \{\mathbf{p}_{s_j} \in \mathbb{R}^3, j = 1, \dots, n_S\}$ denote the detected stem's point-cloud of $n_S \in \mathbb{N}$ points of position \mathbf{p}_{s_j} (Fig. 3a, cyan points). From \mathcal{S} , to retrieve the stem's base \mathbf{p}_{sb} , we take uppermost point of \mathcal{S} with respect to $\{w\}$. Hence, the stem's base \mathbf{p}_{sb} is assumed to be static and is identified only once when the stem is detected.

All scene points that do not belong to \mathcal{S} can be considered as potential obstacles, but we limit our search for obstacles in an area closely around the stem. Hence, by filtering the non-stem scene points and keeping only the ones adequately close to the target stem, i.e. within a pre-specified distance $r_o \in \mathbb{R}$ from the stem's base, the obstacle point-cloud subset of $n_O \in \mathbb{N}$ points is denoted as $\mathcal{O} : \{\mathbf{p}_{o_k} \in \mathbb{R}^3, k = 1, \dots, n_O\}$, with vector \mathbf{p}_{o_k} describing their position (Fig. 3a, blue points).

In order to calculate the free-space point towards which the grape should be pulled (i.e. pull-point), we define a sphere $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$ with the stem's base \mathbf{p}_{sb} as its center and a radius equal to the average stem's length l . Subset \mathcal{O} points are then projected upon this sphere's surface with $\mathcal{O}_{pr} : \{\text{proj}_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{p}_{o_k}) \in \mathbb{R}^3, k = 1, \dots, n_O\}$ denoting the set of these projected points and $\text{proj}_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{p}_{o_k})$ their position vector (Fig. 3b, purple points) given by: $\text{proj}_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{p}_{o_k}) = \frac{\mathbf{p}_{o_k} - \mathbf{p}_{sb}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{o_k} - \mathbf{p}_{sb}\|} l + \mathbf{p}_{sb}$. Notice that in [32] spherical projection has been used for the purpose of scene coverage planning. The most distant free-space point \mathbf{p}_F from all projected obstacles may be found by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\mathbf{p}_F = \underset{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)}{\text{argmax}} \left\{ \min_{\forall k} \{\|\mathbf{p} - \text{proj}_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{p}_{o_k})\|\} \right\}, \quad (2)$$

(a) Scene's point-cloud \mathcal{W} . Obstacles \mathcal{O} : blue. Stem \mathcal{S} : cyan. Identified stem's base: blue \mathbf{x} . (b) Obstacles projection \mathcal{O}_{pr} : purple. Near-obstacles sampled points: black.

(c) Free-space sphere points: green. Near-obstacles sampled points: black. (d) Free-space hemisphere: green. Obstacles \mathcal{O} : blue. Plane fitted into \mathcal{O} : black lines.

Fig. 3: Point-cloud processing example from lab experimentation with a Real-Sense camera and a mock-up (plastic) grape. Axis Z : camera's view direction. All axes are in meters (m).

with its minimum distance from surrounding projected obstacles being $d_f = \min_{\forall k} \{\|\mathbf{p}_F - \text{proj}_S(\mathbf{p}_{o_k})\|\}$.

In order to deterministically solve (2), sphere $S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$ may be uniformly sampled utilizing any existing sampling methodology. Assuming adequate sampling, the sampled sphere points nearest to \mathcal{O}_{pr} points are found and then removed from the sphere's surface, leaving the remaining sphere surface points, which constitute the free-space surrounding the grape's stem (Fig. 3c). Since the camera cannot see behind obstacles (e.g. leaves, target grape cluster), we apply PCA on subset \mathcal{O} to calculate the corresponding two major eigenvectors i.e. the two direction vectors where most \mathcal{O} data reside; this two vectors define a representative plane fitted into \mathcal{O} (Fig. 3d, black lines). Any free-space point upon the sphere's surface which is behind this plane, is considered invalid. Hence, the previously defined sphere becomes a hemisphere, ensuring that the determined free-space always resides within the camera's clearly visible field of view (Fig. 3d). Given a relatively low number of free-space points via appropriate selection of the sphere's sampling rate, (2) can be solved with brute force in a short amount of time. Notice that the spherical sector, denoted as \mathcal{C} and involving all points $\mathbf{p}_\sigma \in S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$ with $\{\mathbf{p}_\sigma : \|\mathbf{p}_F - \mathbf{p}\| < d_f, \forall \mathbf{p} \in S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)\}$, is the spherical sector with the largest free-space area upon the sphere $S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$ surface (green area in Fig. 4a). The pull-point \mathbf{p}_{gd} is calculated as the point most distant from the camera arm end-effector \mathbf{p}_c on the boundary of the sphere sector \mathcal{C} at its intersection with the plane defined by the three points $(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, \mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_F)$ (Fig. 4b):

$$\mathbf{p}_{gd} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}, \phi_f)(\mathbf{p}_F - \mathbf{p}_{sb}) + \mathbf{p}_{sb}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}, \phi_f)$ denotes the rotation matrix of rotation around $\mathbf{s} = \frac{(\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_{sb}) \times (\mathbf{p}_F - \mathbf{p}_{sb})}{\|(\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_{sb}) \times (\mathbf{p}_F - \mathbf{p}_{sb})\|}$ by $\phi_f = \arccos\left(1 - \frac{d_f^2}{2l^2}\right)$ rads; angle ϕ_f is the angle between $\mathbf{p}_F - \mathbf{p}_{sb}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{gd} - \mathbf{p}_{sb}$ vectors.

Table I summarizes the classified/calculated point-cloud subsets.

Remark 2. In this paper, we utilize the Fibonacci lattice methodology to sample $S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$, which is a fast and near optimal way of sampling a sphere. Furthermore, in [33] a method to find the closest Fibonacci point for a given point

(a) Green area: largest free-space area, i.e. spherical sector \mathcal{C} , upon sphere $S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$ surface. (b) Top view of the three points $(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, \mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_F)$ plane, intersecting with sphere sector \mathcal{C} .

Fig. 4: Pull-point \mathbf{p}_{gd} considered for the grape manipulation.

Point-cloud Subsets	Involved Points
whole scene : \mathcal{W}	$\mathbf{p}_{w_i} \in \mathbb{R}^3, i = 1, \dots, n_W$
stem : $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{W}$	$\mathbf{p}_{s_j} \in \mathbb{R}^3, j = 1, \dots, n_S$
obstacles : \mathcal{O} , non-stem points $(\mathcal{W} - \mathcal{S})$ within r_o distance from \mathbf{p}_{sb}	$\mathbf{p}_{o_k} \in \mathbb{R}^3, k = 1, \dots, n_O$
proj. obstacles : $\mathcal{O}_{pr} \triangleq \text{proj}(\mathcal{O})$ upon $S(\mathbf{p}_{sb}, l)$	$\text{proj}_S(\mathbf{p}_{o_k}) \in \mathbb{R}^3, k = 1, \dots, n_O$

TABLE I: Point-cloud Classification.

upon the sphere is introduced, allowing the match of the sphere projected obstacle points \mathcal{O}_{pr} to corresponding Fibonacci points without resorting to an exhaustive search that would significantly increase the calculation cost.

B. Camera Arm Control - Reaching & Unveiling Tasks

The control law for the camera arm is presented in details in [26] and utilized in this paper, so that the camera arm achieves its control objectives (Subsection II-A). A brief description of the [26] control scheme is given below for completeness.

The camera arm end-effector's reference velocity is calculated by the superposition of two reference velocity control terms, the ROI *reaching with centering* control signal $\mathbf{V}_{cr} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ and the stem *unveiling* control signal, $\mathbf{V}_{cu} \in \mathbb{R}^6$:

$$\mathbf{V}_c = \mathbf{V}_{cr} + \mathbf{V}_{cu}, \quad (4)$$

When there are no stem points detected ($n_S = 0$), $\mathbf{V}_{cu} = \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 1}$ by design and \mathbf{V}_{cr} is acting alone. Such a case may occur at the start of the harvesting process, when the camera is far from the ROI and the stem is initially not detectable until the ROI is approached or entered. For the task we consider in this work, Figure 5 illustrates a typical initial and final state of the camera's motion under the superimposed velocities.

1) *Reaching and centering reference velocity:* To achieve the *reaching with centering* objective, the following control signal is utilized [26]:

$$\mathbf{V}_{cr} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} k_{cp} \max(0, f(\mathbf{e}_{pc})) \mathbf{e}_{pc} \\ k_{co} \theta \mathbf{k} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $k_{cp}, k_{co} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ are constant positive gains for translation and orientation respectively, $\mathbf{e}_{pc} = \mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_c$ and $f(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{x} - r^2$ for any $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$; $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$ and \mathbf{k} are the angle and axis of the minimum rotation between \mathbf{e}_{pc} and

Fig. 5: Camera arm control methodology. (a) Initial state. (b) Desired state.

the camera axis \mathbf{z}_c , which can be calculated by the following expressions:

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\mathbf{z}_c^\top \mathbf{e}_{pc}}{\|\mathbf{e}_{pc}\|} \right), \quad \mathbf{k} = \frac{\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{z}_c) \mathbf{e}_{pc}}{\|\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{z}_c) \mathbf{e}_{pc}\|} \quad (6)$$

with $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{z})$ the skew symmetric matrix of the corresponding vector \mathbf{z} . Notice that \mathbf{V}_{cr} is continuous and its value is zero if and only if $f(\mathbf{e}_{pc}) \leq 0$ and $\theta = 0$.

2) *Unveiling Reference velocity*: To increase the unveiled region around the visible stem points \mathbf{p}_{s_j} , a reference velocity is designed in [26] to rotate the camera in a way that increases the distance of the camera ray to \mathbf{p}_{s_j} from the surrounding obstacles. The approach utilizes a barrier artificial potential field $V(\hat{r}_{j,k})$ around each spherical obstacle k centered at \mathbf{p}_{o_k} points of the obstacle point-cloud \mathcal{O} , having a radius d_o selected to cover the empty space between neighboring points. The potential field is smoothly activated only within a predefined distance $d_a \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ from this obstacle's surface:

$$V(\hat{r}_{j,k}) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \ln^2 \left(\frac{d_a^2}{d_a^2 - (d_a - \hat{r}_{j,k})^2} \right), & \text{if } \hat{r}_{j,k} < d_a \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{r}_{j,k}$ is the distance of the ray to \mathbf{p}_{s_j} from the k -th obstacle surface (Fig. 5). The field induces a corresponding virtual repulsive velocity $\mathbf{u}_{j,k}$ at $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k}$ which is the point on the ray with the minimum distance from the obstacle point \mathbf{p}_{o_k} (Fig. 5) and is given by:

$$\mathbf{u}_{j,k} \triangleq -\frac{\partial V(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k})}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k}} = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{d_a^2 - (d_a - \hat{r}_{j,k})^2} \ln \left(\frac{d_a^2}{d_a^2 - (d_a - \hat{r}_{j,k})^2} \right) \mathbf{e}_{j,k}, & \text{if } \hat{r}_{j,k} < d_a \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

with $\mathbf{e}_{j,k} \triangleq (d_a - \hat{r}_{j,k}) \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{o_k}}{\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{o_k}\|} \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

This repulsive velocity $\mathbf{u}_{j,k}$ is realized through a rotation $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{j,k}$ around the axis normal to vectors $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{s_j}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{j,k}$, passing from \mathbf{p}_{s_j} :

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{j,k} \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{S}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{s_j})}{\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{s_j}\|^2} \mathbf{u}_{j,k}, & \text{if } \left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j}^\top}{\|\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j}\|} \right) \bar{\mathbf{p}}_{co_k} \in (0, \|\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j}\|) \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

with $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j} = \mathbf{p}_{s_j} - \mathbf{p}_c$ and $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{co_k} = \mathbf{p}_{o_k} - \mathbf{p}_c$. Notice that the condition in (9) translates into considering only the obstacle points between the camera and the stem for the calculation of $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{j,k}$, i.e. the obstacles that can actually hinder the cutter's approach and reaching to the stem. Summing the $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{j,k}$ -s deriving from all $n_{\mathcal{O}}$ surrounding obstacles and acting on the j -th pivot point, yields:

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{s_j} \triangleq \sum_{k=1}^{n_{\mathcal{O}}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_{j,k} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (10)$$

that is the total angular velocity for the j -th stem's point. The total unveiling velocity \mathbf{V}_{cu} is then computed by summing $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{s_j}$ for all stem points and calculating the corresponding linear velocity at the camera arm end-effector:

$$\mathbf{V}_{cu} \triangleq k_c \sum_{j=1}^{n_s} \left[\mathbf{S}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j}) \right] \boldsymbol{\omega}_{s_j} \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (11)$$

where $k_c \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is a positive, tunable gain, while $\mathbf{S}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j})$ is the skew symmetric matrix of the corresponding vector $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{cs_j}$.

C. Grasping Arm Control - Manipulation Task

To realise the grasping arm's control objective (Subsection II-B), reference velocity \mathbf{V}_g is designed as a force/position controller, presented below:

$$\mathbf{v}_p = -k_{pg} (\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} - \mathbf{n}_c \mathbf{n}_c^\top) \mathbf{e}_{pg} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_f = -k_{fp} \mathbf{n}_c \mathbf{e}_{fg} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_{pg} = \mathbf{p}_g - \mathbf{p}_{gd} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{e}_{fg} = \mathbf{n}_c^\top f - f_d \in \mathbb{R}$ are the position and force errors, $k_{pg}, k_{fp} \in \mathbb{R}$ are positive, control gains and

$$\mathbf{n}_c = \frac{\mathbf{p}_{gd} - \mathbf{p}_{sb}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{gd} - \mathbf{p}_{sb}\|}. \quad (14)$$

is the direction from the stem base to the pull-point.

The force control signal (13) is applied in the direction of \mathbf{n}_c (14) to maximize the stem's stretching at the end of its motion (Fig. 6) and the position control signal (12) along the space orthogonal to \mathbf{n}_c . Both signals contribute to the motion of the grasped grape towards its final position which is determined by the projection of the space target \mathbf{p}_{gd} on the space orthogonal to \mathbf{n}_c , while the position on the \mathbf{n}_c direction is indirectly determined by the achievement of the stretching force. Regarding the orientation of the grasped grape cluster, let the grasped grape's direction coincide with one of the axes of the grasping arm end-effector's frame $\{G\}$, which is assumed to be the y_g -axis $\mathbf{y}_g \in \mathbb{R}^3$ (Fig. 6). The following proposed signal:

$$\mathbf{v}_{g\omega} = -k_{og} (\mathbf{n}_c \times \mathbf{y}_g) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \quad (15)$$

with k_{og} a positive gain, aligns the arm's end-effector/grasped grape's direction \mathbf{y}_g with the stretched stem's \mathbf{n}_c , facilitating further the harvesting process by avoiding any stem obstructions, as well as introducing a human-inspired manipulation of the target grape (see Fig. 1), where in the final configuration just before the stem's cutting, the human hand along with the grasped grape are aligned with the grape's stem.

Combining (12), (13) and (15), the reference velocity \mathbf{V}_g regarding the grasping arm's end-effector is:

$$\mathbf{V}_g = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_{gt} \\ \mathbf{v}_{g\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_p + \mathbf{v}_f \\ \mathbf{v}_{g\omega} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 6: Grasping arm force/position and orientation control. Force control (13) applied at \mathbf{n}_c . Position control (12) applied at subspace $\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} - \mathbf{n}_c \mathbf{n}_c^\top$. Orientation control aligns \mathbf{n}_c with \mathbf{y}_g .

with $\mathbf{v}_{gt} = \mathbf{v}_p + \mathbf{v}_f \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the grasping arm's translational velocity.

D. Bimanual Robot Motion Coordination

In order for the camera arm to follow the grasping arm's motion while keeping the stem unveiled and centered within the in-hand camera viewpoint (Fig. 2 - coordinated asymmetrical), the grasping arm's translational velocity is superimposed to the camera arm's reference velocity as follows:

$$\mathbf{V}'_c = \mathbf{V}_c + \left[\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{v}_{gt}) \frac{\mathbf{v}_{gt}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{sb} - \mathbf{p}_c\|} \right] \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{v}_{gt})$ is the skew symmetric matrix of \mathbf{v}_{gt} . The rotational part is a feedforward term that compensates the centering error induced by this addition. As centering errors are regulated by \mathbf{V}_c , which is still applied in (17), the rotational part is not necessary but helps in smaller centering error transients and faster response.

Hence, the reference velocity control signal \mathbf{V}_r regarding the two arms and their coordination involves \mathbf{V}'_c and \mathbf{V}_g for the camera and grasping arm respectively and is mapped to the joint space according to (1) as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger(\mathbf{q})[\mathbf{V}'_c{}^\top \quad \mathbf{V}_g{}^\top]^\top. \quad (18)$$

E. Implementation

To implement a solution that satisfies both the commanded reference signals at the end-effector space as well as safety constraints, such as joint limits, self and obstacle collision avoidance, we adopt a hierarchical constraint strategy with the safety inequality constraints having a higher priority than the task equality constraints and use the hierarchical quadratic programming (HQP) solver of [34] to compute the resulting joint velocities commanded to the robot. Further details can be found in our previous works [27], [35].

The selection of parameter values in the commanded reference signals is made according to the following general guidelines. The ROI radius $r \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is selected based on the camera specifications and the stem detection requirements. The radius of the spherical obstacles d_o is selected to cover the empty space between neighboring points, hence it depends on the point cloud density. To have a smooth and effective camera motion, the value of d_a should be small so that activation of repulsive velocities are generated only by obstacles close to visible stem points in the camera's view. The desired pulling force magnitude $f_d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is selected at the minimum level possible given the force sensing specifications in order to stretch the target stem without inflicting grape damage or slippage. The control gains $k_{cp}, k_{co}, k_c, k_{pg}, k_{fp}, k_{og}$, that are involved in the generated control signals, regulate the speed of response in the control target achievement and are tuned in order to achieve the control target within reasonable time without incurring very high initial reference velocities which may be unfeasible to track by the real robot.

IV. IN-LAB EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Validation of the proposed methodology was initially performed with lab experiments utilizing two UR5e robotic arms with a control cycle of 2 ms and a mock-up vine illustrated in Fig. 7, involving plastic vine branches and leaves and a plastic grape cluster as the target crop with a stem of length $l_{act} = 0.07$ m colored red in order to get his point-cloud as the proposed method requires. The camera arm (Fig. 7b) was equipped with a Realsense D415 to capture the RGB image and the scene's point-cloud with a frame rate of 30 FPS and a resolution of 848×480 pixels, while a 3D printed mock up of a cutting tool was attached at its tip (Fig. 7b). A 3D printed end-effector was used in the grasping arm holding the mock up grape stably throughout the experiment (Fig. 7c). Hence, for the lab experiments we assume that the target grape grasping task (Fig. 2 - uncoordinated) is considered already completed, hence in the initial stage (Fig. 2) only the camera arm moves for ROI reaching and stem unveiling, followed by the bimanual coordinated task of grape manipulation which is the focus of this work (see Fig. 2 - enclosed in orange dotted line).

The stem is reliably detectable only within a range of 0.7 m from the camera. The ROI is defined as a sphere with radius $r = 0.35$ m centered at the stem's base \mathbf{p}_{sb} so that the ROI reaching command gets the camera arm sufficiently close to the stem. Any non stem points are obstacles, for which we use spheres with radius $d_o = 0.01$ m. The camera arm's control parameters were selected to be $k_{cp} = k_{co} = 1$ for (5), $d_a = 0.002$ m, $k_c = 0.00001$ for (11). The grasping arm's control parameters in (16) are chosen to be $k_{pg} = 0.6$, $k_{og} = 0.8$, $k_{fp} = 0.025$, with a desired force magnitude of $f_d = 5$ N.

In the overall process, the bimanual coordinated grape manipulation begins once all the following conditions are simultaneously met: the camera reaches at 0.37 m from the detected stem base, and the camera's translational and angular velocities become less than 0.01 m/s and 0.025 rad/s respectively. Figures 8 - 10 depict lab experimental results with the green dotted vertical line at 8.1 seconds marking the start of the bimanual grape manipulation. Figures 8a, 8b, 8c depict the stem region reaching distance, the centering angle and the unveiled stem points demonstrating that the proposed controller ensures ROI reaching and camera centering. In Fig. 8a, 8b just before the start of the grape manipulation task (green dotted line) the stem base position is updated and in turn the center of ROI, which explains the observed discontinuity.

Fig. 7: (a) Lab setup. (b) Camera arm. (c) Grasping arm initial state.

(a) *Reaching*. Desired region radius $r = 0.35$ m - red dashed line. (b) *Centering*. Angle θ between $\mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_c$ and camera's view direction \mathbf{z}_c .

(c) *Unveiling*. Visible stem points with respect to camera.

Fig. 8: In-lab experimentation - Camera arm control.

(a) Position error.

(b) Grasped grape/Arm's end-effector alignment with stretched stem.

(c) Measured applied force. Desired force $f_d = 5$ N - red dashed line.

Fig. 9: In-lab experimentation - Grasping arm control.

At the beginning of the coordinated motion, the distance of the camera from the stem and its centering is affected by the grape manipulation which explains the temporary drop in the number of visible stem points (Fig. 8c) right after the beginning of the bimanual motion (8.1 – 10 sec), but this is quickly corrected via the camera arm control (17) that keeps the stem unveiled. In general, the number of visible stem points (Fig. 8c) is increased during the camera arm initial motion (0 – 8.1 sec) and further raised during the grape's manipulation, when the stem is stretched. Figure 9 depicts the grasping arm's position error and force response in the respective sub-spaces achieving the desired stretching force of 5 N as well as its desired axis alignment. The spike at 8.1 seconds (green dotted line) denotes the reference velocity control activation of the grasping arm (13). Figure 10 shows the camera's viewpoint at the beginning of the lab experiment (Fig. 10a), at the start of the bimanual

Fig. 10: In-lab experimentation - In-hand camera's viewpoint. (a) Process start. (b) Bimanual motion's start. (c) End of overall task.

grape manipulation (Fig. 10b) and at the end of the grape manipulation task (Fig. 10c), where the stem is stretched and fully visible enabling the stem cutting task.

V. IN-FIELD EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The BACCHUS harvesting platform with ZED2 side cameras and lidars equipped with two UR10e arms one with a gripper with 3D-printed fingers and the other with a ZED-mini camera and an electrical cutting tool is utilized (Fig. 11) for extensively evaluating the proposed method in a real vineyard via the evaluation of the whole harvesting pipeline described in Section II and shown in Fig. 2.

The control parameters for the region reaching and visual unveiling signal are $r = 0.3$ m, $d_o = 0.01$ m, $k_{cp} = k_{co} = 20$, $d_a = 0.002$ m, $k_c = 0.0001$, while for the manipulation task signal are $k_{pg} = 0.25$, $k_{og} = 0.5$, $k_{fp} = 0.004$, $f_d = 6.5$ N.

Figure 12 shows the grasping arm results from an indicative in-field experiment demonstrating the achievement of the desired goals within the pre-specified error thresholds of 0.01m, 0.1rad and 1N from the target values. The spike at approximately 20 seconds is due to the motion status transition at the grape manipulation task's completion. The calculated pull-point \mathbf{p}_{gd} towards which the grasped grape is pulled is marked with a red dot in Figure 12d, depicting the scene point-cloud captured by the in-hand camera, with stem points in cyan and obstacles points in blue. Snapshots of the initial and final state of the grape's manipulation task are depicted in Fig. 13.

In a total of 95 conducted field experiments, the whole harvesting pipeline was successful 69 times with a mean duration of $T = 61.5s$ per grape. From this duration 23.5s was spent for grape grasping, manipulation and stem cutting

Fig. 11: BACCHUS bimanual harvesting platform. Right top - Camera arm with cutter and mounted in-hand camera. Right bottom - Grasping arm with specialised gripper.

Fig. 12: In-field experimentation - Grasping arm control.

(a) Initial (top) and final (bottom) arms states.

(b) Initial (left) and final (right) grape states.

Fig. 13: In-field experimentation - Initial and final states of manipulation. (a) Scene overview. (b) Zoom on grape.

while initial stem detection took 8.5s. The remaining time was needed to transfer the grape to the basket and move to the next harvesting position. Out of the 26 failed cases, 12 of them were caused due to a failure to grasp the grape caused by target pose errors or contact of the gripper with the vine branches because of poor lighting conditions that hinder the system's perception quality. From the rest failed cases, 5 were due to failed stem detection, 4 due to failed cutting and 5 due to the grape's slippage.

A video showing a lab experiment (Section IV), as well as indicative results from the BACCHUS in-field trials (both successful and failed), can be found in the following link: <https://youtu.be/a7r8OzKVHJM>.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a bimanual control methodology for reaching a pre-cut state regarding the target grape cluster's stem is presented. Control methods are designed for end-effector velocities for the camera and the grasping arm in order to reach and unveil the stem as well as manipulate the grape to generate

space around the stem. Lab experimentation as well as real in-field experiments conducted in a real wine grape vineyard validate the methodology's success, which can be generalized on other crop types as well. The proposed method requires continuous and reliable visual feedback and stem recognition which is affected by lighting conditions and speed of robot motions. This can be considered a limitation of the proposed method and our future work aims to develop a method that requires only a few camera views to achieve the same result faster instead of an on-line visual feedback. Future work is also planned for a sensorized gripper via tactile sensors to allow a more gentle and effective grape manipulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Framework Programme Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No 871704, project BACCHUS.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Marinoudi, C. G. Sørensen, S. Pearson, and D. Bochtis, "Robotics and labour in agriculture. a context consideration," *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 184, pp. 111–121, Aug. 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2019.06.013>.
- [2] M. Eberhardt and D. Vollrath, "The effect of agricultural technology on the speed of development," *World Development*, vol. 109, pp. 483–496, Sept. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2016.03.017>.
- [3] F. A. Fathallah, "Musculoskeletal disorders in labor-intensive agriculture," *Applied Ergonomics*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 738–743, 2010, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2010.03.003>.
- [4] F. Yandun Narvaez, G. Reina, M. Torres-Torriti, G. Kantor, and F. A. Cheein, "A survey of ranging and imaging techniques for precision agriculture phenotyping," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 2428–2439, 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMECH.2017.2760866>.
- [5] M. H. Ko, B.-S. Ryuh, K. C. Kim, A. Suprem, and N. P. Mahalik, "Autonomous greenhouse mobile robot driving strategies from system integration perspective: Review and application," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 1705–1716, 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMECH.2014.2350433>.
- [6] R. R. Shamschiri, C. Weltzien, I. A. Hameed, I. J. Yule, T. E. Grift, S. K. Balasundram, L. Pitonakova, D. Ahmad, and G. Chowdhary, "Research and development in agricultural robotics: A perspective of digital farming," *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1–11, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.25165/j.ijabe.20181104.4278>.
- [7] L. F. P. Oliveira, A. P. Moreira, and M. F. Silva, "Advances in agriculture robotics: A state-of-the-art review and challenges ahead," *Robotics*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/robotics10020052>.
- [8] L. Droukas, Z. Doulergi, N. L. Tsakiridis, D. Triantafyllou, I. Kleitsiotis, I. Mariolis, D. Giakoumis, D. Tzovaras, D. Kateris, and D. Bochtis, "A survey of robotic harvesting systems and enabling technologies," *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems*, vol. 107, no. 21, Jan. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10846-022-01793-z>.
- [9] P. Li, S. heon Lee, and H.-Y. Hsu, "Review on fruit harvesting method for potential use of automatic fruit harvesting systems," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 23, pp. 351–366, 2011, doi: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.11.2514>.
- [10] Y. Onishi, T. Yoshida, H. Kurita, T. Fukao, H. Arihara, and A. Iwai, "An automated fruit harvesting robot by using deep learning," *ROBOMECH Journal*, vol. 6, no. 13, pp. 2–9, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40648-019-0141-2>.
- [11] A. Silwal, J. R. Davidson, M. Karkee, C. Mo, Q. Zhang, and K. Lewis, "Design, integration, and field evaluation of a robotic apple harvester," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 1140–1159, Sept. 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/rob.21715>.
- [12] S. Hayashi, K. Ganno, Y. Ishii, and I. Tanaka, "Robotic harvesting system for eggplants," *Japan Agricultural Research Quarterly: JARQ*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 163–168, 2002, doi: <https://doi.org/10.6090/jarq.36.163>.

- [13] E. J. V. Henten, J. Hemming, B. van Tuijl, J. Kornet, J. Meuleman, J. Bontsema, and E. van Os, "An autonomous robot for harvesting cucumbers in greenhouses," *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 13, pp. 241–258, 2002, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020568125418>.
- [14] Q. Feng, W. Zou, P. Fan, C. Zhang, and X. Wang, "Design and test of robotic harvesting system for cherry tomato," *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 96–100, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.25165/j.ijabe.20181101.2853>.
- [15] S. Hayashi, K. Shigematsu, S. Yamamoto, K. Kobayashi, Y. Kohno, J. Kamata, and M. Kurita, "Evaluation of a strawberry-harvesting robot in a field test," *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 105, no. 2, pp. 160–171, Feb. 2010, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2009.09.011>.
- [16] C. Smith, Y. Karayiannidis, L. Nalpantidis, X. Gratal, P. Qi, D. V. Dimarogonas, and D. Kragic, "Dual arm manipulation—a survey," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 60, no. 10, pp. 1340–1353, 2012, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.robot.2012.07.005>.
- [17] R. Herguedas, G. López-Nicolás, R. Aragüés, and C. Sagüés, "Survey on multi-robot manipulation of deformable objects," in *2019 24th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, 2019, pp. 977–984, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ETFA.2019.8868987>.
- [18] M. Abbas, J. Narayan, and S. K. Dwivedy, "A systematic review on cooperative dual-arm manipulators: modeling, planning, control, and vision strategies," *International Journal of Intelligent Robotics and Applications*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 683–707, Dec 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41315-023-00292-0>.
- [19] T. Yoshida, Y. Onishi, T. Kawahara, and T. Fukao, "Automated harvesting by a dual-arm fruit harvesting robot," *ROBOMECH Journal*, vol. 9, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40648-022-00233-9>.
- [20] T. Li, F. Xie, Z. Zhao, H. Zhao, X. Guo, and Q. Feng, "A multi-arm robot system for efficient apple harvesting: Perception, task plan and control," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 211, p. 107979, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2023.107979>.
- [21] Y. Jiang, J. Liu, J. Wang, W. Li, Y. Peng, and H. Shan, "Development of a dual-arm rapid grape-harvesting robot for horizontal trellis cultivation," *Frontiers in Plant Science*, vol. 13, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.881904>.
- [22] Y. Zhao, L. Gong, C. Liu, and Y. Huang, "Dual-arm robot design and testing for harvesting tomato in greenhouse," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 49, no. 16, pp. 161–165, 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2016.10.030>.
- [23] X. Ling, Y. Zhao, L. Gong, C. Liu, and T. Wang, "Dual-arm cooperation and implementing for robotic harvesting tomato using binocular vision," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 114, pp. 134–143, Apr. 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.robot.2019.01.019>.
- [24] D. Sepúlveda, R. Fernández, E. Navas, M. Armada, and P. González-De-Santos, "Robotic aubergine harvesting using dual-arm manipulation," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 121 889–121 904, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3006919>.
- [25] T. Yi, D. Zhang, L. Luo, and J. Luo, "View planning for grape harvesting based on active vision strategy under occlusion," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 2535–2542, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/LRA.2024.3357397>.
- [26] D. Papageorgiou, L. Koutras, and Z. Doulgeri, "A controller for reaching and unveiling a partially occluded object of interest with an eye-in-hand robot," in *2022 IEEE-RAS 21st International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids)*, 2022, pp. 254–260, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/Humanoids53995.2022.10000171>.
- [27] S. Stavridis, P. Falco, and Z. Doulgeri, "Pick-and-place in dynamic environments with a mobile dual-arm robot equipped with distributed distance sensors," in *2020 IEEE-RAS 20th International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids)*, 2021, pp. 76–82, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/HUMANOIDS47582.2021.9555672>.
- [28] L.-E. Montoya-Cavero, R. Díaz de León Torres, A. Gómez-Espinosa, and J. A. Escobedo Cabello, "Vision systems for harvesting robots: Produce detection and localization," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 192, p. 106562, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2021.106562>.
- [29] I. Kleitsiotis, I. Mariolis, D. Giakoumis, S. Likothanassis, and D. Tzovaras, "Anisotropic diffusion-based enhancement of scene segmentation with instance labels," in *Computer Analysis of Images and Patterns*, N. Tsapatsoulis, A. Panayides, T. Theoharides, A. Lanitis, C. Pattichis, and M. Vento, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 383–391, doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-89131-2_35.
- [30] G. Zampokas, I. Mariolis, D. Giakoumis, and D. Tzovaras, "Residual cascade cnn for detection of spatially relevant objects in agriculture: The grape-stem paradigm," in *Computer Vision Systems*, H. I. Christensen, P. Corke, R. Detry, J.-B. Weibel, and M. Vincze, Eds. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023, pp. 159–168, doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44137-0_14.
- [31] A. Sidiropoulos and Z. Doulgeri, "From rgb images to dynamic movement primitives for planar tasks," in *2023 IEEE-RAS 22nd International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids)*, 2023, pp. 1–8, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/Humanoids57100.2023.10375217>.
- [32] R. Border and J. D. Gammell, "Proactive estimation of occlusions and scene coverage for planning next best views in an unstructured representation," in *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2020, pp. 4219–4226, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS45743.2020.9341681>.
- [33] B. Keinert, M. Innmann, M. Sängler, and M. Stamminger, "Spherical fibonacci mapping," *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 1–7, 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2816795.2818131>.
- [34] A. Escande, N. Mansard, and P.-B. Wieber, "Hierarchical quadratic programming: Fast online humanoid-robot motion generation," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 33, no. 7, pp. 1006–1028, 2014, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0278364914521306>.
- [35] S. Stavridis and Z. Doulgeri, "Bimanual assembly of two parts with relative motion generation and task related optimization," in *2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2018, pp. 7131–7136, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS.2018.8593928>.

tion, optimization and human-robot interaction.

ing and manipulation, control of uncertain robotic systems and human-robot interaction.

UK. Her current research interests include the topics of physical human robot interaction, robot teaching and learning by demonstration, bimanual mobile robots, object grasping and manipulation with analytical and data based learning methods and the control of uncertain robotic systems. She is currently an evaluator of Horizon Europe research and innovation projects.

Sotiris Stavridis received his Diploma in electrical and computer engineering from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece in 2017. He has worked as a research associate in various European projects, with his work published in scientific conferences and journals. He is currently working as a research associate in the Automation and Robotics Laboratory, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (ARL-AUTH). His research interests include bimanual manipulation, mobile manipulation,

Leonidas Droukas received his Diploma in electrical and computer engineering from the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece in 2008 and the Ph.D. degree in electrical and computer engineering from the same department in 2016. He has worked as a researcher in various projects both European and national. He is currently working as a Postdoctoral Researcher in the Automation and Robotics Laboratory, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (ARL-AUTH). His research interests include object grasping and manipulation, control of uncertain robotic systems and human-robot interaction.

Zoe Doulgeri Zoe Doulgeri (IEEE senior member) is a Professor of Robotics and Control of Manufacturing Systems and the director of the Automation and Robotics Lab of the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH). She received the diploma of Electrical Engineering from AUTH and an M.Sc. (DIC) in Control Systems, an M.Sc.(DIC) in Social and Economic Aspects of Science and Technology in Industry and a Ph.D in Mechanical Engineering, from the Imperial College, London,